

A STUDY TO EVALUATE THE SLEEP DISTURBANCE AMONG STAFF NURSES OF TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL NAWABSHAH

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Abstract

Background: Sleep disturbance is a widespread health issue. Sleep disturbance is a common problem among staff nurses due to shift work, long duty hours, night shifts, less work experience and work related stress. Poor sleep can affect nurse's physical health, mental well-being, work performance and quality of patient care. This study aimed to assess the level of sleep disturbance among staff nurses of tertiary care hospital Nawabshah.

Methodology: A descriptive cross sectional study was conducted at Peoples Medical College Hospital (PMCH) Nawabshah. Total sample size was 187 which was selected through non-probability convenient sampling technique. The data was collected through General sleep disturbance scale (GSDS) to assess the variety of sleep issues over the last 7 days from staff nurses by using Likert scale of 8 points 0=never to 7=everyday. The collected data was analyzed by using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Descriptive statistics, including frequencies and percentages, were used, and results were presented in the form of tables and figures.

Results: The results showed that the 77 (41.2%) were mild sleep disturbance, 56 (29.9%) had moderate sleep disturbance, 50 (26.7%) had normal sleep (no sleep disturbance) and only 4 (2.1%) Participants were severe sleep disturbance.

Conclusion: The study concludes that the majority of participants were mild Sleep disturbance, only 2.1 % of participants were severe sleep disturbances.

INTRODUCTION

Sleep disturbance is a common health issue worldwide. Sleep disturbance as trouble falling asleep, early awakening, short sleep duration and excessive daytime fatigue are more common factors in nurses than the general population and also the factors like stress and aging negatively impact the sleep quality and can cause both physical and psychological problems for nurses as well as for general population.¹ The

literature showed that there are conditions of sleep disturbances including insomnia, hypersomnia, parasomnia sleep disorders, restless leg syndrome (RLS) and sleep apnea.² Night shifts in nurses can disrupt melatonin production which cause sleep disturbances.³ During the covid-19, nurses experienced significant mental challenges due to sleep disturbance because of day and night duty shifts.⁴ As sleep disturbance is

more common in women due to menstrual issues.⁵ Risk of depression, anxiety and cardiovascular diseases also increase due to sleep disturbance and sleep disorders.⁶ Study have found that women's sleep quality is more effected by high sugar consumption than that of man and caffeine also lead sleep disturbance in females.⁷ The natural secretion of cortisol also leads to sleep disturbance in staff nurses due to night shift work.⁸ Sleep disturbance not only affect health but also affect the performance of nursing care they provide, it affect their overall performance and results in the healthcare settings and insufficient sleep impacts cognitive and behavioral functions, and the risk of injuries and infections, reduces the nursing care quality, and leads to more errors in the workplace.⁹ Research indicate that significant percentage of nurses all over the world experience sleep disturbance due to harsh schedules and high stress environments, in numerous studies with poor sleep quality reported as 66% of nurses in the US, 78% in UK, 54.6% in Italy, 79.8% in South Korea, 76.3% in China, 77.1% in Nigeria and 70.6% in Ethiopia experience high sleep disturbance.¹⁰ The effort-reward imbalance (ERI) model by siegrist (1996) showed that when nurses don't receive enough pay, it causes stress, sleep problems and higher desire to leave job.¹¹ Nurses experience various types of sleep disturbance, while more

than 88% suffering from insomnia and about 60% to 80% complain of poor sleep quality and these are associated with several demographic factors, such as gender, single marital status, younger age, less clinical experience, family history of mental disorders, lack of leisure activities, poor physical activity, and poor health and working in an tertiary care hospital with long work hours and high patient intake also cause sleep disturbance.¹²

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The quantitative cross sectional study design was conducted at Peoples medical college hospital (PMCH) Nawabshsh. The duration of study was two months from 17 November 2025 to 17 January 2026 after approval of Institutional Review Board (IRB), Sample size was 187 which was selected from Staff nurses of PMCH and non-probability convenience sampling technique was used to select Participants.

The inclusion criteria included the Staff nurses full time working at Tertiary care hospital Nawabshsh, age 18 years and above, both male and female and participants who was willing to participate in study was included. And the exclusion criteria was the Participants who was unavailable during data collection period, those who was on sick leave or maternity leave and Individual aged < 18 years was excluded.

RESULTS

CLASSIFICATION OF SLEEP DISTURBANCE AMONG STAFF NURSES

Table 1: Gender of Participants

Gender	Frequency	Percent %
Male	105	56.1%
Female	82	43.9%
Total	187	100.0%

Table 2: Religion of Participants

Religion	Frequency	Percent %
Muslim	172	92.0%
Hindu	14	7.5%
Christian	1	.5%
Total	187	100.0%

Table 3: Ethnicity of Participants

Ethnicity	Frequency	Percent %
Sindhi	135	72.2%
Panjabi	28	15.0%
Baloch	17	9.1%
Muhajar	4	2.1%
Others	3	1.6%
Total	187	100.0%

Table 4: Marital status of Participants

Marital status	Frequency	Percent %
Single	37	19.8%
Married	150	80.2%
Total	187	100.0%

Table 5: Socioeconomic status of Participants

Socioeconomic status	Frequency	Percent %
Poor class	3	1.6%
Middle class	158	84.5%
High class	26	13.9%
Total	187	100.0%

Table 6: Educational level of Participants

Educational level of participants	Frequency	Percent %
BSN	153	81.8%
Masters	29	15.5%
PhD	5	2.7%
Total	187	100.0%

Table 7: Work Experience of Participants

Years of Experience	Frequency	Percent %
No experience (Fresh)	37	19.8%
1	1	.5%
10	22	11.8%
11	2	1.1%
12	3	1.6%
13	3	1.6%
14	1	.5%
15	11	5.9%
16	3	1.6%
17	2	1.1%
18	3	1.6%
19	1	.5%
2	11	5.9%
20	4	2.1%
25	1	.5%
3	12	6.4%
4	17	9.1%

5	15	8.0%
6	20	10.7%
7	3	1.6%
8	14	7.5%
9	1	.5 %
Total	187	100.0 %

Table 8: ASSESSMENT OF SLEEP DISTURBSNCE

How often in the past week did you:	No days F (%)	1day F (%)	2days F (%)	3days F (%)	4days F (%)	5days F (%)	6days F (%)	7days F (%)
Have difficulty getting to sleep	108(57.8%)	23(12.3%)	13(7.0%)	11(5.9%)	7(3.7%)	10(5.3%)	4(2.1%)	11(5.9%)
Wakeup during your sleep period	98(52.4%)	15(8.0%)	14(7.5%)	13(7.0%)	14(7.5%)	7(3.5%)	4(2.1%)	22(11.8%)
Wakeup too early at the end of a sleep period	109(58.3%)	15(8.0%)	15(8.0%)	12(6.4%)	13(7.0%)	6(3.2%)	5(2.7%)	12(6.4%)
Feel rested upon awakening at the end of a sleep period	38(20.3%)	11(5.9%)	16(8.6%)	15(8.0%)	22(11.8%)	19(10.2%)	18(9.6%)	48(25%)
Sleep poorly	108(57.8%)	21(11.2%)	20(10.7%)	8(4.3%)	11(5.9%)	5(2.7%)	4(2.1%)	10(5.3%)
Feel sleepy during the day	112(59.9%)	15(8.0%)	18(9.6%)	15(8.0%)	11(5.9%)	7(3.7%)	3(1.6%)	6(3.2%)
Struggle to stay awake during the day	116(62.0%)	18(9.6%)	10(5.3%)	17(9.1%)	8(4.3%)	6(3.2%)	10(5.3%)	2(1.1%)
Feel irritable during the day	106(56.7%)	18(9.6%)	17(9.1%)	22(11.8%)	11(5.9%)	4(2.1%)	3(1.6%)	6(3.2%)
Feel tired or fatigued during the day	96(51.3%)	12(6.4%)	21(11.2%)	16(8.6%)	21(11.2%)	7(3.7%)	5(2.7%)	9(4.8%)
Feel satisfied with the quality of	54(28.9%)	14(7.5%)	17(9.1%)	20(10.7%)	17(9.1%)	9(4.8%)	12(6.4%)	44(23.5%)

your sleep								
Feel alert and energetic during the day	63(33.7%)	16(8.6%)	11(5.9%)	11(5.95%)	17(9.1%)	15(8.0%)	10(5.3%)	44(23.5%)
Get too much sleep	112(59.9%)	18(9.6%)	10(5.7%)	20(10.7%)	13(7.0%)	9(4.8%)	3(1.6%)	2(1.1%)
Get too little sleep	105(56.1%)	15(8.0%)	12(6.4%)	21(11.2%)	13(7.0%)	6(3.2%)	4(2.1%)	11(5.9%)14
Take a nap at a scheduled time	114(61.0%)	14(7.5%)	13(7.0%)	17(9.1%)	10(5.3%)	11(5.9%)	5(2.7%)	3(1.6%)
Fall asleep at an unscheduled time	80(42.8%)	15(8.0%)	18(9.6%)	17(9.1%)	19(10.2%)	11(5.9%)	6(3.2%)	21(11.2%)
Drink an alcoholic beverage to help you get to sleep	135(72.2%)	9(4.8%)	13(7.0%)	11(5.9%)	11(5.9%)	2(1.1%)	2(1.1%)	4(2.1%)
Use tobacco to help you get to sleep	150(80.2%)	9(4.8%)	9(4.8%)	10(5.3%)	2(1.1%)	4(2.1%)	2(1.1%)	1(.5%)
Use herbal product to help you get to sleep	139(74.3%)	15(8.0%)	9(4.8%)	6(3.2%)	8(4.3%)	4(2.1%)	3(1.6%)	3(1.6%)
Use an over the counter sleeping pill to help you get to sleep	144(77.0%)	9(4.8%)	13(7.0%)	12(6.4%)	8(4.3%)	00 (%)	00(%)	00 (%)
Use a prescription sleeping pill to help you get to sleep	144(77.0%)	12(6.4%)	6(3.2%)	13(7.0%)	8(4.3%)	1(.5%)	3(1.6%)	00(%)
Use aspirin or other pain medication to help you get to sleep	155(82.9%)	9(4.8%)	5(2.7%)	5(2.7%)	6(3.2%)	3(1.6%)	39(1.6%)	1(.5%)

DISCUSSION

In this study there was assessed the sleep disturbance among staff nurses of tertiary care

hospital Nawabshah and also compared with the past studies. Regarding the demographic variables, in this study the results concluded as

the mean age of participants was 36.86 with SD \pm 5.035, the previous study showed that the mean age of participants were 32.54 years with SD \pm 7.32.¹ According to gender results showed that the majority of participants 105 (56.1%) were male while only 82 (43.9%) of participants were females and previous study showed that the majority of the participants (91.1%) were females.¹ According to religion results revealed that the majority of participants 172 (92.0%) were Muslims, 14 (7.5%) participants was Hindu, and only 1 (.5%) participants was Christian. Residual status showed that the 120 (64.2%) of participants were from Urban areas while 67 (35.83%) participants were from Rural areas it means that the majority of participants was from Urban areas and about the socio economic status 158 (84.5%) of participants belonged to middle class, 26 (13.9%) belonged to high class and only small portion 3(1.6%) belonged to poor class, showed that the majority of participants belonged to middle socio-economic class. study showed that most of the participants 135 (72.2%) belonged to Sindhi ethnicity, 28 (15.0%) were Panjabi, 17 (9.1%) were Baloch, 4 (2.1%) were Muhajar and only 3(1.6%) belonged to other ethnic group. According to marital status results concluded as the majority of participants 150 (80.2%) were married and only 37 (19.8%) were single and there was not belonged to divorced status, and previous study also showed that the majority of participants (72.1%) was married.¹³ As according to educational level results showed that majority of participants 153 (81.8%) held Bachelor's degree in Nursing, 29 (15.5%) of participants held Masters and only 5 (2.7%) held the PhD and according to previous study most of the participants (52.2%) also held bachelor's degree (BSN), (30.2%) Participants held diploma and (17.6%) participants held master's degree.¹⁴ The work experience of participants was Mean = 8.13 years with SD \pm 4.968 but previous study showed that the work experience of participants was 9.30 years with SD \pm 7.05, with (67.1%).¹ According to findings among staff nurses of tertiary care hospital Nawabshah results revealed that the majority of participants 77 (41.2%) belonged to mild sleep disturbance, 56 (29.9%)

had moderate sleep disturbance, 50 (26.7%) had normal sleep (no sleep disturbance) and only 4 (2.1%) were severe sleep disturbance, showed that the prevalence of sleep disturbance among staff nurses at tertiary care hospital Nawabshah is at mild range there is not found severity of sleep disturbance among staff nurses but according to previous study the nearly half (46.9%) of participants reported sleep disturbance some with moderate sleep disturbance and only small portion belonged to normal sleep (GSDS \geq 43).¹ Studied concludes that the sleep disturbance among staff nurses is caused by high workload, heavy patients outcome changing shift schedules as night duties, new environment as newly offered nurses (no experience) stress, anxiety and less work experience and some studied also showed that that married nurses suffer more in sleep disturbance than the unmarried nurses¹⁵.

CONCLUSION

The study about sleep disturbance among staff nurses was concluded by using the General sleep disturbance scale (GSDS) reveals insight into the sleep health of nursing professionals.

The findings showed that more than just a small part of the nurses experience different levels of sleep disturbances, categorized into four groups = normal sleep, mild sleep disturbance, moderate sleep disturbance and severe sleep disturbance.

The results showed that the 50(26.7%) of the participants reported normal sleep (No sleep disturbance) suggesting that about one fourth of the sample maintains healthy sleep pattern, 77(41.2%) suffering from mild sleep disturbance, 56(29.9%) were moderate sleep disturbance and 4(2.1%) of the participants facing severe sleep disturbance.

The high prevalence of mild to moderate disturbances highlights that sleep quality among staff nurses potentially affecting their performance, patient care and overall well-being.

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